

**EVALUATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF THREE
VARIETIES OF SOYBEANS (GLYSINE MAX) FLOUR GROWN IN
ZAMFARA STATE**

BY

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ABSTRACT

Three different varieties of soybeans (Glycine max) TGX-1440-2, TGX-1448-2, TGX-1776-2 were used to produce soy flour using roasting and steeping method. Results from proximate analysis shows no significance in their ash, and crude fibre content of the two varieties. The carbohydrate and the protein content differs with roasting samples having amount of protein (48%, 42% and 45%) for R. TGX-1440-2, R. TGX-1776-2, respectively with steeping method which has ((40%, 38%, and 39%), for S.TGX-1440, S. TGX-1448-2 and S. TGX-1776-2. Steeping method produce higher values of carbohydrate 34.50%, 35.00% and 35.60% for S.TGX 1440-2, S.TGX-1448-2 and S.TGX1776-2 while roasting method has 27.90%, 34.9% and 31.70% for R. TGX1440-2, R.TGX-1448-2 and R.TGX-1776-2 respectively. The moisture content of steeping method (8%, 10% and 9%) is also greater than that of roasting method (7%, 6%, and 7%). Both methods have no significant difference in their physico-chemical properties except in the appearance, with roasted methods giving brown colour while steeping gave creamy colour. There are little or no significant difference in their functional and rheological properties in the methods.

Key words: Soybeans, TGX, Roasting, Steeping, Proximate analysis

INTRODUCTION

Soybeans which is scientifically called Glycin max is a specie of legume, native of East Asia widely grown for its edible bean with its numerous uses (Enwere, 1998). It originates from Southern Asia and was first domesticated by Chinese farmers around 1100BC. By the first century, soybeans were grown in Japan and other countries. Soybeans is very nutritious, the protein and the oil components in soybean are not only in high quality but also in high quantity. Soybean contain high proportion of unsaturated fatty acid, so it is a healthy oil. Soybean contain all the essential amino acids most of which are present in amounts that closely match those required for human and animal development (Akobundu et al (1982).

In Africa and the rest of the developing world, where malnutrition due to inadequate protein prevalence there is urgent need to explore the utilization of plant protein in the formulation of new food products or in conventional foods (Khalid et al, 2003). This is predicated on the fact that animal protein such as meat, milk and eggs are expensive and relatively difficult to come by (Chal-Guerrero et al, 2002). Mustapha et al, (1989) and Uwaegbute (1987), posited that soybean are of different types (Yellow, Black and Green). Although its global production has been on the rise, its estimated demand of about 300 million tons exceeds the current supply by over 40 million tons (FAOSTAT, 2010)

All soy flours gives a protein boost to recipes. Soy flour is 50% protein (Mustapha et al, 1986). However, defatted soybean is an even more concentrated source of protein than full fat soy flour. There are three kinds of soy flour available, natural or full-fat, which contains the natural oils found in the soybean is made from unextracted dehulled beans and contains about 18-20% oil, defatted which has the oil removed during processing from solvent extracted flakes contains less than 1% lecithinated oil. Because of the fatty nature of soybean, the plant is classified as an oil seed rather than a pulse. Fat-free (defatted) soybean meal is significant and cheap source of protein for animal feed (Enwere 1998).

Unprocessed soybean has undesirable flavor and bitterness. It contains the toxic proteins haemagglutinins and anti-trypsin. These substances must be destroyed or inactivated to make the bean palatable and digestible both for human and animal consumption (Aykroyd and Doherty 1982). Soybean can be processed into soy milk, soy sauce, tofu (soybean curd), yoghurt, soybean sprouts, tempeh (soy steak) soy flour and other products. Soybean can be used for the manufacture of protein isolates and concentrates (Akroyd and Dohearty 1982). Soy flour is most widely used in baked goods, 2-15% is added to breads, crackers, muffins, donuts, cakes, rolls, cookies, tortillas, or chapattis. It is also used in pasta products (spaghetti, noodles, macaroni) processed meats (sausages, bologna, frankfurters meat loaves), gravies, sauces, soups, cereals, prepared mixes (pan cake and waffle). In other products, it generally lowers the cost and improves the functional properties by serving as a conditioner, emulsifier, moisture retainer antioxidant and or extender (Peter et al, 2003). Other uses as soy flour includes production of soy milk, as an inexpensive and cholesterol free egg substitute in food as a starting material for the preparation of infant formulae, protein concentrate or isolate (Peter et al 2003).

METHODOLOGY

Soybeans Milling

Soybeans were procured from Kaura Namoda market in Zamfara state. The varieties were identified at the department of crop science Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The soybeans was cleaned to remove all unwanted materials such as dust, chaffs, dirt and other foreign matters. 600g was weighed and washed. The cleaned bean was dried in an oven at 650C for 12hrs, it was then removed and allowed to cool on a clean plastic bowl. The dried soybean were roasted at 900C and allowed to cool. The soy beans was dehulled, to separate or remove the seed coat. The roasted soybeans was milled using hammer mill.

Figure 1: Flow Chart for the production of soybeans flour using steeping and roasting methods

Moisture Content Determination

The product is disintegrated to give smaller surface area. The weight of Petri dish to be used was taken and recorded. 2g of the samples were measured into a Petri dish of a known weight. The samples were heated at a temperature of 120oC for 2 hours and its weighed was detained. The heating was repeated for 30 minutes at the same temperature and the weight was taken repeatedly. This procedure was repeated until a constant weight was obtained.

The moisture content was calculated using the equation below:

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = \frac{W2 - W3}{W2 - W1} \times 100$$

Where W1 = initial weight of empty crucible

W2 = Weight of crucible + sample before drying

W3 = Weight of crucible + sample after drying

Ash Content Determination

2g of flour sample was weighted into a crucible. The weighed sample was put on Bunsen flame inside a fume cupboard to drive off most of the smoke. The sample was transferred into a pretreated muffle furnace at 550oC and left at this temperature for 2 hours until a light grey ash resulted. When the colour of the residue became black in colour, it was moisture with a small amount of water to dissolve the salt. The sample was dried in the oven and the ashing process repeated. It was cooled in a desiccators and re-weighed. The ash content as described was calculated using the equation below:

$$\text{Weight of Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of original sample} \times (W3 - W1)}{W2 - W1}$$

Where;

W1 = Weight of empty crucible

W2 = Weight of crucible + sample before ashing

W3 = Weight of crucible + ash

PROTEIN CONTENT DETERMINATION

Kjeldhal method is one of the methods for determining crude protein food product. It involves three stages digestion, distillation and titration of crude value obtained by multiplying the nitrogen value by 6.25. Procedure Protein content was determined using Kjeldal method, 5 grams of the sample was transferred into a macro digestion flask and 8g of NaSO₄ was added to it. 25ml concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to the mixture, the flask and its content were heated in a Bunsen burner inside a fume cupboard to compel poisonous gases out. Heating continued for 1 hour until the mixture became clear. It was allowed to cool 400ml of ammonia free water was added to the digests. 50ml of 2% boric acid and 1ml of methylated indicator was measured into a receiving flask of 500ml capacity. The delivery tube tip was dipped not too far into boric acid as the digest was made alkaline with 75ml of 5% NaOH, distillation then proceeded. 250ml of distillate was collected in a beaker and condenser was washed into 50ml ammonia free water into the distillate. The distillate collected or obtained was titrated with 0.1N H₂SO₄ and result recorded.

$$\% N_2 = \frac{0.014 \times M \times V \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

% crude protein = % Nitrogen (N₂) x 6.25

Where M = Actual molarity of acid

V = Volume of acid used

Fat Content Determination

The empty crucible was weighed. 2g of the sample was weighed into a crucible. The crucible with the sample was placed in a furnace to burn to ashes at temperature of 550°C for 12 minutes. The ash sample was cooled in a desiccator and then weighed

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ fat content} = \frac{\text{Gram of fat in sample} \times 100}{\text{Gram of dried sample}}$$

Carbohydrate Determination

According to Badejo (1999), basic food analysis consists of determination of moisture, fibre and ash. Therefore, the total carbohydrate was determined by difference when the sum of the percentage moisture, ash, crude fibre and protein was subtracted from 100 (analysis %)

% total carbohydrate = 100 – the analysis %

Functional Properties Determination

Functional properties have been defined by Matil (1971) as those characteristics that governed the behavior of nutrients in food during processing, storage and preparation as they affect quality and acceptability. Some important functional properties that influence the utility of certain food are water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity, emulsion capacity, foam ability etc. the practical determination of some of these functional properties shall be considered

Bulk Density

The method used by Akpapunam and Markakis (1981) was used. 5g of the sample was weighed and transferred into a 50ml graduated cylinder and the volume was noted. The bulk density of the packed sample was calculated after tapping the cylinder for several times until the sample stopped setting after about 2 minutes The bulk density was calculated by dividing the ratio of the mass of the sample by the settled volume

$$\text{The bulk density (g/ml)} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}{\text{Volume of Sample (ml)}}$$

Water absorption capacity

2g of the sample was blended with 100ml distilled water in a whirling blender and the suspension was whipped at 1600rpm for 5 minutes. The mixture was poured into a 250ml measuring cylinder and recorded after 30 seconds. The foaming capacity is expressed as percentage increase in volume according to the formula of Abbey and Ibeh (1988).

$$\text{Foaming capacity} = \frac{\text{Vol. after whipping} - \text{Vol. before whipping}}{\text{Volume before whipping} \times 100}$$

Emulsification capacity

The method of Beuchat, Cherry and Quinn (1955) was used. 2g flour sample with 100ml of water were blended at room temperature for 30 seconds in a blender at 1600rpm. After complete dispersion, 25ml of refined oil was added continually for another 30 seconds until phase separation occurred. Then it was transferred into a centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 1600rpm for 5 minutes. The volume of oil separated from the sample after centrifuging was read directly. Emulsification capacity was expressed as the amount of oil capacity emulsified as milliliter of oil emulsified per gram of protein

$$\text{Emulsification capacity} = \frac{X \times 100}{Y}$$

Where: X = Height of emulsification

Y = Height of whole solution centrifuge tube

Oil absorption capacity

This was determined according to the method described by Beuchat (1977). 1g of sample was mixed with 10ml of oil for oil absorption in a Kenwood blender for 30 seconds. The sample was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 25°C for 30 minutes and centrifuged. The volume of supernatant in a graduated cylinder was noted. Density of oil was taken to be 1g/ml.

Dispersibility

This was determined by the method described by Kulkarni (1991). 10g of flour was suspended in 100ml of measuring cylinder and distilled water was added to reach a volume of 100ml. the setup was stirred vigorously and allowed to settle for 3 hours the volume of settled particles was recorded and subtracted from 100ml. the difference was reported as percentage dispersibility

Gelation capacity

The method of Coffman and Garcia (1977) was adopted. Sample dispersion of 2-20% (W/V) were prepared in 5ml distilled water. The test tubes containing these suspensions were heated for 1 hour in a boiling water bath followed by rapid cooling under running cold tap water. The tubes were further cooled for 30 minutes at 4°C. The gelatin capacity is the least (lowest gelatin concentration determined as the concentration when the sample from the inverted test – tube did not fall or slip.

Wettability

The wettability was determined for the flour sample according to the method of Regenstein (1984). 2g each of the flour sample were weighed separately in a sieve and transferred to a beaker containing 80ml distilled water and magnetic stirrer without stirring the water. The behavior of the flour was observed on the water surface immediately after adding the sample. After 30 minutes observation, the material was stirred on the magnetic stirrer sufficiently fast to form a vortex which reached the bottom of the beaker. The stirring continued for one minute and after which the grade describing wettability was recorded as excellent, good fair or poor according to the time and behavior of the dispersion.

Digestibility

The protein in soybean meal is very digestible, but a high portion of the protein in alfalfa (which is largely bound to the plant cell wall) is indigestible to rabbits. Rabbits digest cellulose poorly (Frage, 1990). This seems a paradox for an animal that lives naturally on vegetation. But this is part of the plant. The low digestibility of fiber and rapid elimination of large, hard – to – digest particles enable the rabbit to maintain a higher level of feed intake than it would otherwise be able to (Sakaguchi, 1992).

Physico – Chemical Properties Determination

Titratable Acidity

The titratable acidity was determined as described by Pearson (1970). 5g of the flour sample was weighed into 50ml of water and allowed to stand for 30 minutes in 40oC water bath. Using phenolphthalein as indicator, the filtered solution was titrated with 0.5N NaOH.

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ Acid value} = 1\text{ml of } 0.5\text{N NaOH} = 0.0068\text{g}$$

The pH was determined as described by FAO (1992). 5g of flour sample was weighed into 50ml water. It was allowed to stand for 30 minutes in 40oC water bath. The solution was filtered and the pH was determined using a pH meter.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Result of Proximate Analysis

Samples/parameters	STEERING METHOD			ROATING METHOD			LSD
	S.TXG 1440-2	S.TG-1448-2	S.TGX-1776-2	R.TGX-1440-2	R.TGX-1448-2	R.TGX-1776-2	
Moisture	8.00 ^a ±0.04	10.00 ^a ±0.01	9.00 ^a ±0.01	7.00 ^a ±0.02	6.00 ^a ±0.00	7.00 ^a ±0.02	0.63
Protein	40.00 ^a ±0.02	38.00 ^a ±0.00	39.00 ^a ±0.02	48.00 ^b ±0.02	42.00 ^a ±0.01	45.00 ^a ±0.03	0.35
Ash	5.00 ^a ±0.06	5.00 ^a ±0.02	4.60 ^a ±0.02	3.60 ^a ±0.01	4.00 ^a ±0.01	3.30 ^a ±0.02	0.48
Fat	9.90 ^a ±0.01	8.00 ^a ±0.02	9.30 ^b ±0.00	10.00 ^a ±0.03	9.60 ^b ±0.03	9.50 ^b ±0.00	0.52
Crude fibre	2.60 ^a ±0.01	4.00 ^a ±0.01	3.00 ^a ±0.02	3.50 ^a ±0.02	3.50 ^a ±0.02	3.50 ^a ±0.02	0.26
CHO	34.50 ^a ±0.32	35.00 ^a ±0.23	35.10 ^a ±0.21	27.90 ^a ±0.11	34.90 ^a ±0.12	31.70 ^b ±0.22	1.04

Values are means ± standard deviations of duplicate duplications. Means in row with same superscript are not significantly ($p>0.05$) different Legends: S = Steeping R = Roasting

Table 2: Results of Functional Properties

Samples/parameters	STEERING METHOD			ROATING METHOD			LSD
	S.TXG 1440-2	S.TG-1448-2	S.TGX-1776-2	R.TGX-1440-2	R.TGX-1448-2	R.TGX-1776-2	
BD (g/ml)	1.56 ^a ±0.01	1.66 ^c ±0.00	1.61 ^b ±0.01	1.56 ^a ±0.01	1.66 ^c ±0.02	1.61 ^b ±0.02	0.17
EC (g/ml)	35.00 ^a ±0.02	35.00 ^a ±0.02	35.00 ^a ±0.02	35.00 ^a ±0.02	35.00 ^a ±0.04	35.00 ^a ±0.00	0.10
FC (g/ml)	16.28 ^a ±0.02	16.25 ^b ±0.03	16.35 ^b ±0.03	16.23 ^a ±0.01	16.28 ^a ±0.01	16.35 ^a ±0.02	0.09
WAC (g/g)	6.05 ^a ±0.02	6.04 ^a ±0.01	7.00 ^b ±0.00	6.05 ^a ±0.01	6.00 ^a ±0.04	7.00 ^b ±0.03	0.22
OAC (g/g)	10.00 ^a ±0.00	9.20 ^b ±0.01	8.10 ^a ±0.02	9.10 ^b ±0.04	9.00 ^b ±0.05	8.00 ^a ±0.03	0.31
D (%)	5.70 ^a ±0.02	1.66 ^c ±0.03	1.61 ^b ±0.02	1.56 ^a ±0.02	1.66 ^c ±0.02	1.61 ^b ±0.02	0.08
W (min)	1.50 ^a ±0.00	1.70 ^a ±0.05	1.60 ^b ±0.03	1.70 ^a ±0.02	1.70 ^a ±0.03	1.80 ^a ±0.04	0.05
GC (%)	4.00 ^a ±0.04	6.00 ^a ±0.02	7.00 ^a ±0.03	5.00 ^b ±0.02	4.00 ^a ±0.03	7.00 ^a ±0.02	0.11

Values are means ± standard deviations of duplicate duplications. Means in row with same superscript are not significantly ($p>0.05$) different. BD=bulk density, EC=emulsification capacity, FC=foaming capacity, WAC=water absorption capacity, OAC=oil absorption capacity, D=dispersibility, W=wettability, GC=gelation capacity Legends: S= Steeping R = Roasting

Table 3: Result of Physio – Chemical Properties

Physico-chemical properties	STEEPING METHOD			ROASTING METHOD			LSD
	S.TGX-1440-2	S.TGX-1448-2	S.TGX-1776-2	R.TGX-1440-2	R.TGX-1448-2	R.TGX-1776-2	
Titration Acidity	0.29 ^a ±0.02	0.28 ^a ±0.02	0.26 ^a ±0.01	0.28 ^a ±0.03	0.29 ^a ±0.03	0.25 ^a ±0.02	0.04
pH	7.23 ^a ±0.02	7.25 ^a ±0.02	7.33 ^a ±0.01	7.26 ^a ±0.01	7.27 ^a ±0.02	7.33 ^a ±0.00	0.06
Appearance	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream	-

Values are means ± standard deviations of duplicate duplications. Means in row with same superscript are not significantly ($p>0.05$) different. Legends: S = Steeping R = Roasting

DISCUSSION

The result of the proximate analysis of the soybean flour as shown in table 1 there was significant difference ($p<0.05$) in terms of the proximate analysis of the steeping and roasting methods of the soybeans flour samples, the moisture, protein, ash, fat, crude fibre and carbohydrate content range from 6.00-10.00%, 38-45%, 3.30- 5.00%, 8.00-10.00%, 2.60-4.00% and 27.90-35.10% respectively. Which indicate that samples of the roasting method contains higher amount of protein (48%, 42% and 45%) for (R-TGX-1440-2, R-TGX-1448-2, and RTGX-1776-2) respectively compared to steeping method which are (40%, 38% and 39%) for (S-TGX-1440-2, S-TGX-1448-2 and S-TGX-1776-2) respectively which agrees with the work of Peter et al, (2003).R-TGX – 1440-2 has the highest protein content of 48% of the three (3) different varieties analyzed. This shows that roasting method retain more protein during processing than the steeping methods. The action of heat on the flour particles might have toughened the cells against possible denaturation of protein from the cell matrix. STGX-1776-2 has the highest carbohydrate content of 35.10% with 39% protein content. The high protein content in soybean flour suggests that its importance in formulation of baby foods and other related foods rich in protein in food industries. The high ash content in all the varieties shows that, they all contain high amount mineral which is an important dietary requirement in the body. The difference in the fat content as indicated between the steeping and the roasted could be attributed to the action of heat which might have cost the fats to leach during roasting.

Table 2 shows the functional properties of the three different varieties of soybean flour produced. The bulk density, emulsification capacity, foaming capacity, water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity, dispersibility, wettability and gelation capacity which ranged from 1.56-1.66g/ml, 35.00g/ml, 16.25-16.35gml, 6.00-7.00g/g, 8.00-10.00g/g, 1.56-5.70%. 1.50-1.80min and 4.00-7.00% respectively, There was no significance difference ($p>0.05$) in the emulsification capacity but there was significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the titrable acidity but there was significance difference ($p<0.05$) in the pH of the samples. The pHs of the sample are basically neutral. The roasted sample turns brown which might have occur as a result of caramelization (action of heat on carbohydrate sugar), the steeping methods samples shows creamy colour (appearance).

CONCLUSION

From the results of the analysis, it was observed that the three (3) samples (TGX-1440-2, TGX-1448-2, and TGX-1776-2) are all rich in protein, but the protein varied by the type of method used for processing the flour. Roasting method may retain more protein than the one processed by steeping method. Soy flour produced by roasting method is more preferred for industrial application since it contains higher amount of percentage protein and fat than the steeping method. Roasted soy flour also has reduced level of moisture which prevents the growth of microorganisms and reduced spoilage. The anti – trypsin factors that interfere with the digestive enzymes are removed by roasting which makes it more acceptable in industries.

It is thus recommended that the three (3) varieties of soybean flour produced by both roasting and steeping method contain high protein level, and can be used by industries in the production of high protein foods. – It is also recommended that the roasting method be adopted for the processing of soybean flour since it retains more protein.

Further research work should be carried out on the nutritional and microbial quality of different varieties of soybean flour produced by both roasting and steeping methods.

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